

THE EFFECTIVENESS OF MICROSOFT OFFICE 365 AS AN ONLINE ENGLISH LEARNING MEDIA

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ABSTRACT

This study aims whether: 1) Microsoft Office 365 is more effective than conventional methods in teaching writing; 2) Microsoft Office 365 is more effective than other online learning media ;3) There is an increasing interest in language learning; and 4) there is an interaction between teaching methods and students' creativity in learning English. This quasi-experimental research was conducted at Saint Peter's Middle School in the 2020/2021 academic year. The sample of this study has six classes, namely the experimental class which is taught using Microsoft Office 365 and the use of Zoom as an online meeting. Each class consists of 17-22 students, with a total sample value of 60 students. Samples were obtained using cluster random sampling technique. The results showed that there was an increase in the average score and implied that Microsoft Office 365 is an effective method in teaching writing and is suitable to be applied to those who have high creativity.

Keywords: *Office 365, Microsoft, Learning Media, English Learning*

INTRODUCTION

During the literacy period during this pandemic, especially in the education system, the operation and operation of technology have come an obligation to be used in knowledge recently, at least for the last two times. In addition to scholars being suitable to enjoy and observe better in the knowledge process, preceptors can also be eased and helped in guidance and freedom in literacy (Mishra, et. el 2020). Although of course face-to- face guidance or direct literacy between preceptors and scholars in the classroom cannot be compared with online knowledge literacy operations, at least the operation of learning media can be veritably helpful and fix knowledge problems in former literacy. Until now, there has been numerous technology-grounded knowledge operations in colorful stages and bias applied in operations, both web literacy, and installed bones. Palacios et. el (2015), argues that the effect can be observed that the operation of technology- grounded online knowledge can contribute significantly to both training and knowledge in recent times. While it remains that the collaboration of seminaries, parents, and academic instructors is significant, scholars can handpick when and how they learn. It is also suggested that learners, especially immature learners in operations can take part in ideas, exchange ideas, and elaborate their own science. Wang and Zhou (2019) state that multimedia assignments cannot be disassociated from the operation and leverage of social media. Social media correspondents as Bing, Google, Twitter, and blogs are truly greasing in easing independent online knowledge of learners so that they can willingly relate and express ideas about what they experience. Still, the development of ideas that are not educational and indeed false is truly close to social media. In this case, instructors and parents need to choose social media knowledge that is coherent and productive in knowledge, as long as it's liked by scholars. It's believed that it takes suitable training and training staff to conclude and embrace social media so as not to be out of date with the learners (Brown, 2020).

Some experts theorize that sociable media can grease online knowledge and be easy to apply in knowledge. Still, Martens, H., & Hobbs, R. (2015), argue that caution in choosing media is still demanded to keep the pupil literacy system under control. To refer it, social media is intermediated by using electronic and computer communication impulses that allow people to produce, take ideas, and exchange data on the internet. It's truly important that social media is also a collection of special communication networks that are free to interact with multitudinous people around the world (Salloum, et.el, 2017). Social media has come a means of message for all people in all intersections of the world as long as they are connected to the internet. In the selection of learning social media, decision-makers (instructors, seminaries, and parents) must consider the effectiveness and effectiveness of knowledge problems. Thus, decision-makers can get input from social media knowledge that has been proven to be effective. One knowledge platform with effective social media is the apps set up in Office 365. Office 365 is cross-platform messaging, and the meet service is held by Microsoft.

Picture 1: Submenu of Microsoft Office 365

It allows learners to shoot textbook dispatches and voice dispatches, make online match and videotape calls, and share illustrations, forms, stoner locales, and other midpoints. This web assignment runs on the mobile bias but is also suitable to apply to desktop computers, as long as the stoner's mobile scheme remains compounded to the Internet while they use the desktop operation as well (Maderick, et. el, 2016). The service makes stoners bear users in furnishing a standard cellular mobile number for registering with the service. In enlightening use, this operation for being used together, it also applies to use group which is named Microsoft Armies as part of Office 365. In agreement to do better applied of these operations, the preceptors also use some corridor of web apps in Office 365 to validate the predicated knowledge runs well. Office 365 is a web service which is developed by Microsoft for seminaries that makes to simplify designing assignments. The main purpose of Microsoft is to streamline the process of sharing lines between instructors and scholars. It integrates documents, wastes,- correspondence, and timetables into a cohesive platform to manage pupil and school teacher communication (Al Salman, et. el, 2021). Both of these operations have been a corridor of the Indonesian education ecosystem by furnishing, perfecting, and distributing quality education for educators and scholars.

In the specialized operation, videlicet the use of social media, the experimenter applies the knowledge that's applied online by using the two operations in seminaries in North Jakarta where the researcher is also a preceptor at the academy. In targeting or getting successful literacy, similar as grounded knowledge in social media, it's believed that there are several sweats that can be given to learning for scholars, especially youthful scholars. Legg (2016) states that the conditions are to understand the preface of the media, study the prologue of the social media structure, take the substance of knowledge, understand the relationship with the manuals used in the seminary, understand the new meaning according to the field, and relate it to face-to-face knowledge, and test and acclimate understanding and happiness between operations. online and face-to- face knowledge. With these considerations, researchers can see and prove it precisely and effectively. In North Jakarta, especially Kelapa Gading, there are numerous seminaries and universities equipped with well- known libraries and computer laboratories. To make the utmost of this installation, these seminaries, especially vocational seminaries, are constantly using proven operations. Some seminaries, especially those with advanced education systems that use new classes outside the National Curriculum for farther education, are

constantly enriching literacy operations with multi-media knowledge, especially online knowledge (Seminary, 2015). These seminars continuously use books and knowledge sourced from comprehensive online knowledge sources that have been honored by colorful seminars and universities in the world. In addition, because these seminars use online assessments as one of the evaluation evaluations outside of regular examinations, these seminars use books published by well-known publishers as companions for knowledge (Philips, et. el, 2015). The advantage of this operation isn't only to increase interest in knowledge but also to increase the capability to imagine and freedom of expression. One of the seminars that supported this discussion is Saint Peter's School, where the academe applies a regular knowledge system and also uses an online-based knowledge system as supporting material so that the ease of operating online media can be fluently applied.

In order to observe the effect and effectiveness of this operation, this research will focus on the scholars' views and apply them to the questionnaire. By filling out the questionnaire, the instructor can see that some of these two operations are necessary for the scholar. Nevertheless, before studying how to use social media to improve students' knowledge processes, researchers must first understand what scholars think of social media in the classroom. Perception is an external factor that focuses on a person's views, understanding, beliefs, and reactions to an invention. By considering this proposition, this research aims to describe scholars' views on the effectiveness of using Microsoft Office 365 in the process of English knowledge.

METHODOLOGY

According to Forgarty (2018), there are several ways or models to integrate the literacy system, the author chooses the integration model with a qualitative system. This study uses a descriptive qualitative approach to evaluation because this study aims to describe a simple combination of the syllabus. this system is a exploration system that describes or expresses objects in abstract or concrete forms. To support this statement, that qualitative data must be collected through observation ways. The subjects in this study were six classes, which are in grades, and 9 of Junior High School in North Jakarta. The major is taken from the lower secondary position class of English (250 scholars). This study uses a questionnaire to test scholars' comprehensions about the operation of Microsoft Office 365 literacy material in English classes. Experimenters need to know scholars' comprehensions about the material designed for the development of English class chops as the parameter of effectiveness. The exploration data through filling out an online questionnaire with Office 365's form states that perception influences feelings and geste, and influences scholars' beliefs about the literacy terrain. The experimenter provides an evaluation form for scholars to find out their responses to

the design of the perpetration of using Office 365 grounded- literacy accoutrements in English classes that have been developed by experimenters who are also active as preceptors.

Picture 2: Tabmenu of Microsoft Office 365

There are some pointers used in filling out the questionnaire in which are written and surveyed in the table data of Likert. The distributed questionnaire for students' comprehension is about how effective the online media is after the product of web apps is delivered. Data were collected from a questionnaire that was anatomized quantitatively. Instrument data attained from questionnaires about scholars' comprehensions about the perpetration of Microsoft Office 365 in English classes were assessed using a Likert scale grounded on the Likert proposition (1932). The assessment system is carried out appreciatively and negatively. For positive statements, a positive standing system, videlicet A (85-100) which is comprehended as effective, B (65-84) which is comprehended good or standardized, C (51-64) which is comprehended as enough, and D (0-50) which means it's not effective. These data are also anatomized using probabilities. The form of questionnaires was anatomized and data was collected using a Likert Scale. It supposes to measure learners' perspectives about the feasibility of whether social media as learning media still need to be effective or not.

FINDINGS AND RESULTS

Findings

To examine how the learner perceives the application of Office 365-based teaching in Microsoft materials in English lessons, the researcher distributed questionnaires to students, as Office Forms. Data analysis used a Likert scale in which is evidenced by the questionnaires to be distributed from 250 researchers/students. Metrics are used to complete surveys implemented in tables in using web applications. The indicator component consists of relevant applications designed for students. Based on the survey scoreboard, students agree that the Microsoft Office 365 English class application is suitable for the grades and needs, and daily learning habits of students as learners. The researchers concluded that the average student observation was 92, comprehended into that the indicators used to be analyzed for the study generally showed good consistency in their consistent applied study of web apps for the students.

Table: 1 Likert scale

Positive rating score	Category	Negative rating score
A (85 -100)	Effective	D (0 - 50)
B (65-84)	Good	C (51-64)
C (51-64)	Enough	B (65-84)
D (0 - 50)	Not Effective	A (85 -100)

Table: 2 Students' Perception

No	Indicators	Components of Apps	Average score	Classification
1.	The convenience	1. Convenience in Power-automate	96	Effective
		2. Convenience in saving One-drive	94	Effective
		3. Convenience in To-Do	82	Good
2.	The content	1. Content in Power-automate	94	Effective
		2. Content in Streams	94	Effective
		3. Content in Visio	85	Effective
		4. Content in Yammer	94	Effective
3.	The efficiency	1. Efficiency in Sharepoints	95	Effective
		2. Efficiency in Teams and Sway	87	Effective
4.	The language	1. Language in Power-Apps	88	Effective
		2. Language in Word	95	Effective
		3. Language in One-note	91	Effective
5.	The clarity	1. Clarity in Whiteboard	91	Effective
		2. Clarity in Kaizala	92	Effective
		3. Clarity in Sway	92	Effective
6.	The pleasure to use/user indeed	1. User indeed in Powerpoint	92	Effective
		2. User indeed in Kaizala	89	Effective
		3. User indeed in Staff-Notebook	96	Effective
7.	The collaborative use/tag learning	Tag Learning in simultaneous use in Class Notebook, People, and Teams	95	
Total			1744	
Average			92	Effective

Picture 3: Tab menu of Microsoft Office 365 in Button Options

Results

Researchers in this study explain with data that students will be able to use Microsoft 365-based literacy learning, especially in English. In fact, the use of these missions is well-received when students learn to use Office 365, the effective literacy content, well-simplified and understandable to the student, effectively using the language and time used in literacy campaigns. Online educators can understand, that the literacy of application literacy goes well with all educators, the collaborative use of which educators work and collaborate, and the fun to use is based on learning commonly applied on some computers or mobile phones. From the above conclusions and explanations / results, researchers can say that the use of Microsoft Office 365-based literacy materials in English lessons is valid and effective for the mentoring and counseling process. Literacy. This shows that undergraduate students have increased their literacy skills and their interest in using Microsoft Office 365.

CONCLUSION

Microsoft Office 365-based literacy materials in English classes that were created and adapted to strengthening literacy skills in this study met the improvement of learning. This is indicated by the comprehensive results of the students, which at least in this study are numbers that show progress and the learning process is considered effective. This number shows and translates as a perception score that the majority is very good or positive by being verified using a Likert Scale with an effective meaning. The average value of the perceived effectiveness assessment is 92 which indicates that from product factors such as convenience in effective content, effective use of language grammar, clarity in using Microsoft 365, and enjoyment in using the webapp overall, the overall use is very good and is considered effective. in learning English classes in general through Office 365. By using a questionnaire to measure students' opinions and perceptions, it shows that Microsoft Office 365 significantly increases students' literacy interest, especially the operation of online literacy based on online learning through Office 365. Based on the questionnaire analysis, The author concludes that students are effectively recommended to use Office 365.

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